

PHRASEOLOGY AS AN OBJECT OF LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL AND LINGUO-COGNITIVE STUDY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7446519>

Annotation: This article deals with phraseological units as an object of study in different levels. Provisions are formulated for teaching Russian to younger schoolchildren in extracurricular or additional classes in the aspect of mastering the phraseological level. Special culturogenic and linguocognitive properties of a phraseological unit are objects of study and, at the same time, conditions for the effective development of this level.

Keywords: linguoculturology, linguoculture, concept, comparative procedures, language equivalence, miscommunication.

The article presents the necessary grounds for the assimilation of phraseology, as well as the specifics of teaching younger students in additional classes in the Russian language. The purpose of this publication is to identify and analyze the features of the study of phraseological units in elementary school, depending on their linguistic nature. Materials and methods. The material for the publication was programs and textbooks in the Russian language, phraseological dictionaries in the English language. The main research methods were the analysis of scientific literature devoted to the in-depth study of phraseology, as well as descriptive, distributive, linguoculturological. Results. The features of the organization of educational activities in elementary school in the study of the phraseological level of the English language are revealed. Linguistic and cultural features of the semantics of phraseological units are presented as one of the stimulating conditions for the development of these units by schoolchildren. Discussion. The purpose of mastering the philological block of disciplines is to form basic knowledge about the diversity, breadth and at the same time the unity of the cultural and linguistic space of English, which must be solved both using the tools of traditional methods and innovative ones. Conclusion. The study of the phraseological level is characterized as a condition for the formation of communicative competence: phraseological units nominate objects and their features more accurately, and, therefore, communicants, using them in communication, will be able to convey information more vividly, more voluminously, express their attitude to something. Basic provisions: the phraseological level of the language can be systematically and successfully mastered by students in elementary school due to the special linguistic nature; mastering the phraseological level makes it possible to implement the interactive principle of learning; mastering the phraseological level forms the communicative competence of students.

a) Paradigmatic connectedness: characterized by different paradigmatic conditioning and belonging to different lexical-semantic paradigms, lack of semantic continuity;

b) syntagmatic cohesion: characterized by a deterministic contextual interdependence of components, lexical coherence (but not syntactic), subordination of the semantics of the

components to the meaning of the entire phrase, but the ability of the components to destroy syntagmatic barriers and participate in the formation of new contexts;

c)derivational connectedness: characterized by phraseological valency of the elements of the phrase due to polysemy, contextual conditionality of the components, lexical restriction of use in speech (but not semantic), individual motivation and the presence of an internal form mediated by binding to the original phrase, the seeming possibility of a literal interpretation of the phrase.

Linguoculturology that emerged at the crossroads of cultural studies, linguistic and cultural studies, ethnolinguistics and sociolinguistics, interacts with them and has its own integrative aspect of studying the problem of language and culture. It sets the aim of systematic presentation of language and culture units in their correlation, works at a deep level of semantics, taking into account systematic and integrative approaches to these phenomena. Correlating values of culturally determined units with concepts of national culture, linguoculturological analysis provides them with deep and volume explication.

Analysis of the peculiarities of the English national linguistic landscape of the concepts of the concept of "man" and the definition of their indicators using the comparative-typological method and identification of alternatives to the studied linguistic means. Recently, the study of deixis has relied on a practical comprehensive study of deictic tools in world languages rather than just a theoretical study. A lot of information has been collected on the deictic means of different languages. The analysis of the linguocultural and linguocognitive features of the units of the conceptual sphere "Man" led to the following conclusions:

1.The conceptsphere of "Man" as an object of knowledge is a universal phenomenon for all languages and cultures, at the same time, its perception, linguistic occurrence of its features and its importance in categorizing beings are unique to each national language. In this regard, in our study, the idioethnic features of the perception of the world inherent in the English peoples were identified on the example of the conceptsphere "man".

2.The scale of the occurrence of the conceptsphere "Man" in texts of different styles has been studied and they have been comparatively studied within the framework of separate cultural concepts. Although there are some works that study the concept of "man", it is important that it occurs in the context of the text, its place in the semantic field of language was first studied in a monographic plan.

3. Based on the analysis of cognitive linguistics, it is necessary to take into account the typological features of the concept of "man", the formation of mental perceptions, as well as from the point of view of linguocultural studies, mental units have semantic groups according to general and specific features.

4. The study of cases of linguistic realization of the concept of "man" in the compared cultures has the opportunity to reveal their intercultural features. In modern linguistics, the problem of interpreting texts in the language in terms of linguocognitive and linguocultural studies remains relevant. The study of the concept of "man" in the English language in the context of the linguistic world is theoretically and practically important, which further enriched the results of research in the field of linguistics and linguistics. European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements (EJHEA)

5.On the basis of the first systematic analysis of the conceptsphere "man" in the linguistic landscape of English languages, which has not been the subject of special research, the

semantic field and conceptual features of nominative units activated within this conceptsphere are determined.

6. The complete classification of the meanings of the linguistic units belonging to the thematic groups analyzed in the study in terms of human social status, intellect, physical ability, appearance, ability to work, psychological structure improves the existing 20 dictionaries and gives the faith to clearly describe their interpretations.

Linguocultural investigations examine phenomena that bring notional charge. For example, symbolism of color naming include multipurpose, regional, ethnocultural-marked associations. Different notional components are intertwined in it: *Le Rouge et le Noir* (the novel by F. Stendhal with the complex symbolism of the red and the black) *Our future is black* (J. Baldwin on feasible advent of the Black Power) *The Black and the Green* (symbolism of the state flag of Libya) . Focused form of expression, conservation and transfer of value-based connotations are the cultural code. The model of multistage linguocultural semiotic analysis represents the procedure of notional interpretation that contain comparative angle at all stages. The analysis is carried out as exemplified by non-verbal codes of two cultures that allows emphasizing the problem areas: partial divergences and cultural semiotic gaps. The task of notional interpretation of ethnoconnotation is difficult when we face something that does not exist in its environment. During the comparative linguoculturological analysis, the interpretation of ethnocultural notional connotations is carried out in the terms of marks of relevant cultural code.

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